

GENDERED PATTERNS OF ONLINE HATE: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF HOW MALE AND FEMALE CELEBRITIES EXPERIENCE HATE ON SOCIAL MEDIA

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Abstract

This study investigates comments of Instagram users appeared in comment section of International and Pakistani celebrities posts to identify the gendered pattern of engagement of Instagram users. By utilizing qualitative and quantitative content analysis the researchers coded the content and comments were classified into categories based on gender, nationality and framing. The data were analyzed to identify the patterns of comments, treatment and engagements of followers with selected celebrities. The findings suggested that online patterns conforms the offline gender engagement patterns. It underscores that the female celebrities received higher number of comments related to moral judgment, appearance-based criticism and gender based hate than male counterparts who received more supportive or talent-focused comments. Findings also highlighted that Pakistani celebrities followers' comments include body shaming/ appearance attacks, religious and moral policing than international followers. Additionally this study underscores the algorithmic bias related to gender and need for digital policy frameworks to mitigate gendered harassment and create safer digital space.

Introduction

Social media has become a virtual global public sphere; where platforms like Instagram allow millions of users to interact directly with celebrities, making comment sections important section to study public opinion and cultural expressions (Javed, 2025; Rahman et al, 2024; Brooks et al., 2021). Instagram is a popular digital platform among the celebrities and almost all significant celebrities have joined Instagram to connect with their audiences. A significantly large number of fans follow their favorite celebrities for updates and commented on their activities . Therefore, a substantial number of researchers have studied these celebrity pages to understand gendered patterns on social media (Sofeia, & Jingxian, 2025; Azmy et al., 2024; Yuzar et al. 2023; Alfayez et al., 2017; Cook, & Hasmath, 2014). Additionally, the researchers highlighted that the more attention received by a celebrity from their followers online the more there is a chance of getting exposed to harassment (Khan et al., 2025; Gehrke & Amit-Danhi, 2025). A number of research studies observed that these spaces are mirroring the inequalities of the real world offline (Scheffer, 2024; Yasmin, 2023; Pröbster & Marsden 2021; Rosen et al., 2010); gender biases are one of the most visible examples of social inequality online. Researchers also noted that public figures, including female and male celebrities, receive a significantly different treatment of online attention (Javed, 2025; Rahman et al, 2024). It was also observed that women celebrities experience more online gender based harassment than men, reflected a deeper cultural norm and patriarchal power structures (Yasmin, 2023, Battista & Molano, 2023). Hence these celebrity pages and their comments section are excellent resource to identify trends in nature of engagements and treatment with reference to the celebrity's gender and prevailing socio-cultural dimensions. The growing interaction between the celebrities and their followers has blurred the personal and professional space and provide an instant access to their favorite personality. This interaction and overpopulated digital space has also exposed these celebrities to all kind of fans emotion including love and hate to both genders globally. This study is focused to investigate the pattern of fan comments on instagram pages of both local and international celebrities with respect to gender. Through analyzing comment patterns from selected posts, this research tries to understand why gendered inequalities take place in online spaces. (Enock et al., 2024; Horvát & González-Bailón, 2024; Oreoluwa et al., 2024). The approach used in the study allows it to explore how culture interacts with gender and trying to identify how similar or different are these trends for

Pakistani and international female celebrities. In addition to compare the comments, this study also aimed to analyze the frequency and nature of comment posted for female and male celebrities, both Pakistani and international.

Gendered Harassment in Digital Spaces

A growing body of literature shows that online hate is strongly gendered. Studies from South Asia highlighted that women routinely face personal attacks, including body shaming, sexualized remarks, and moral policing, while men are more likely to receive performance based criticism or supportive comments (Mythili & Nagamani 2025; Roiha 2024; Bachmann et al., 2025). It reflected broader patriarchal patterns where women are judged harshly, especially regarding their appearance, moral character, fashion choices, and behavior (Gehrke & Amit-Danhi, 2025). Literature also highlighted that gendered harassment is not limited to Pakistan which indicates that across cultures, women's bodies and morality remain central topics of public discussion, whereas men are allowed more freedom and respect in how they present themselves online (Gehrke & Amit-Danhi, 2025). Online spaces shape how women are seen and judged, even punished in digital spaces, patterns of gendered harassment in Pakistan often carries strong cultural and moral tones (Nanditha et al., 2023; Yasmin, 2025). Although these studies come from different environments, they collectively reinforce the idea that digital misogyny is both global and cultural. The existing literature maintained that the gendered patterns found on digital media platforms are part of a broader social issue that show harassment and violence against female figures is irrespective of the country they belong to.

Global Cultural Patterns of Gendered Hate

The Second major theme shows ties of how gendered hate varies across cultures yet remains consistent. Studies showed that while the expression and intensity of gendered hate differ, the core ideas of controlling women's visibility, regulating their morality, and evaluating their bodies is consistent (Abir & Zrizi 2023; Godinez et al., 2022; Ging & Siapera 2019; Perry & Olsson, 2009). Studies of Pakistani influencers reveal how religious and cultural discussion shape harassment, with clothing based policing and accusations of immodesty frequently directed at women (Zaib et al., 2025; Rahman et al, 2024). This culturally rooted moral policing is less prominent in Western contexts, where harassment often takes the form of sexualization, body shaming, or sarcastic critique (Döring & Mohseni, 2020). Additionally, Nanditha et al. (2023) add that gendered hate globally is tied to broader power structures, with

women in public roles facing harassment designed to silence or discipline them. Similarly, Gehrke and Amit-Danhi (2025) argues that across countries, women experience online violence that mirrors offline inequalities. This literature reviewed under this theme highlighted global pattern of gendered hate and bases both online and offline as an embedded cultural phenomenon.

Gendered Misinformation and Algorithmic Bias

Researchers highlighted how AI moderation in technologies can unintentionally or intentionally create gender bias through datasets that are misogynistic and acting as a catalyst of inequality towards women through algorithmic moderation tools (Karakoç-Keskin & Gül-Ünlü 2025; Battista & Molano 2023). This often overlook harmful content directed at women, allowing hate speech to spread unchecked, hence, creates an additional layer of inequality and echo chambers that again creates algorithmic bias of gendered stereotypes (Jamil et al., 2025; Jeong & Syed 2025; Mpofu, 2025; Veritasia et al., 2025). Additionally, Renan Barzilay, (2019) highlighted that A.I platforms may reproduce gender bias, consequently further harming women and enabling toxic online behavior and creating inequity regimes; these findings are important for understanding how both user behavior and platform structures shape the visibility of gendered hate. Literature reviewed under this theme identified gendered disinformation as a powerful tool used to silence women online, It also revealed that hate against women is not isolated or spontaneous it is often systemic biased and technologically reinforced. Based on the literature reviewed there is a significant gap observed in comparative study of digital behavioral trends among instagram users with reference to Pakistani and International celebrities. That is whether the moral policing, appearance critiques, and objectification observed in literature reflected in broader global patterns or not. To investigate this gap in gendered patterns of instagram users for their favorite celebrities (both international and local) the researchers have designed following research questions:

RQ1. What types of comments were more frequent in male vs female celebrities' comments section?

RQ2. Do the country and culture influence the type of comments received by male and female celebrities?

RQ3. Is there a difference in the way male and female celebrities are treated in their comment section?

Research Methodology

For this study the researchers have utilized qualitative and quantitative content analysis to identify the gendered patterns of online hate and harassment in the comments of followers on celebrity instagram pages. Through qualitative content analysis the researchers have identified the discursive strategies such as moral policing, objectification admiration, and the quantitative content analysis was used to code the data of themes and pattern to identify the frequency difference across the gender and cultural groups such as local versus international celebrities.

The researchers have selected 8 celebrities using purposive sampling including four Pakistani celebrities (2 female and 2 male including Hania Amir, Mahira Khan, Atif Aslam and Fawad Khan) and four international celebrities (2 female and 2 male include Selena Gomez, Zendaya, Timothée Chalamet and Harry Styles). This selection allows a balanced comparison across gender and cultural contexts. Selection criteria included (a) their local and international appeal (b) verified instagram accounts (c) fall under the category of mega influencer that is >1M followers. The selected celebrities were coded as male and female on the basis of their Instagram bios or the pronouns they are using to identify themselves.

Celebrities name and their followers' status

Celebrities	Group	Instagram Followers	Gender	Total Posts
Hania Amir	Pakistani	19.2m	Female	511
Mahira Khan		11.7	Female	1501
Atif Aslam,		11m	Male	636
Fawad Khan		1.7m	Male	266
Selena	International	416m	Female	2143
Zendaya		176m	Female	3500
Timothée Chalamet		19.6m	Male	169
Harry Styles		46.3m	Male	717

Three instagram posts from each celebrity having maximum engagements in the form of comments were selected for this study. The researchers selected top 50 comments from each with maximum replies and are publicly visible. That makes a total of 400 comments from all accounts for this study. Another reason to select the publicly visible comments was that these reflect algorithmic moderation as well. To ensure ethical compliance all usernames, identities and post related details were anonymised to maintain the confidentiality of the instagram users.

To maintain the coding consistency and standardized the thematic analysis in accordance with the international comparison the preferred language for this study is selected as English. Hence all English language comments from the selected instagram profiles were sampled for coding and assessments.

Coding Procedure

Data were coded manually through individual coding, coded sheet were compared and discussion based resolution strategy was adopted to resolve coding anomalies. Mutual agreement was reached through consensus and discrepancies were resolved through category refinement or researcher deliberation. 14 thematic categories were identified through this process. To reduce overlapping, these categories were constructed to be mutually exclusive and distinct; frames were identified as positive, negative and neutral, following a well-defined decision criterion to minimize overlap, such as that sexualization was different from appearance shaming through explicit content

Finding

Female Celebrities

The data (Table-2; Chart-2) revealed an interesting insight to the patterns of gendered online harassment or hate against both local and international female celebrities. Out of total 200 comments a significant number of (67) comment fell under the one category of admiration and praise that makes 33% of the total comments. 32 were found as neutral interaction and 21 are of emotional support. However, the combined data of categories including Body Shaming / Appearance Attacks; Moral/Religious Policing; Sexualization / Objectification; Sexualization / Objectification; Gendered Insults; Humor / Sarcasm; Harassment / Cyberbullying; Ethnic / Nationality Hate; Success-Related Hate also indicated a strong trend of online bullying, hate and harassments faced by the celebrities. Total comments under these categories were 79 (39.5%) where body shaming has the highest ratio of comments that is which makes 30.3% of the total data of negative comments. Moreover it is noted that Ethnic/Nationality hate and comparison categories are among the least populated categories with 2 comments in each. Two female celebrities dominated in admiration category are Pakistani celebrity Hania Amir and International celebrity Selena Gomez with 17 and 20 coments along with Mahira Khan which profile hase 16 comments in all 3 posts. In neutral interaction Mahira Khan (13) and Hania Amir (11) are dominating. Out of 21 comments in emotional supports the Selena Gomez has

highest interaction with 8 comments. Zendaya (30%) has suffered more with body shaming attacks followed by Hania Amir (26%) and Mahira Khan (26%) in Pakistan. Additionally both Pakistani celebrities suffered more with moral and religious policing that is 36.4% Hania and 36.4% Mahira followed by Zendaya 27.2%. It was observed that both Hania Amir (50%) and Selena Gomez (50%) also exposed to Gendered insult while Zendaya (63.6%) and Selena Gomez (27.3%) faced more sexualized comments on their posts.

Table 2: *Female celebrities category-wise comment distribution*

Category	Hania Amir	Mahira Khan	Zendaya	Selena Gomez	Total (Female)
Admiration & Praise	17 (34%)	16 (32%)	14 (28%)	20 (40%)	67 (33.5%)
Neutral Interaction	11 (22%)	13 (26%)	6 (12%)	2 (4%)	32 (16%)
Body Shaming / Appearance Attacks	6 (12%)	6 (12%)	8 (16%)	4 (8%)	24 (12%)
Moral/Religious Policing	4 (8%)	4 (8%)	3 (6%)	0 (0%)	11 (5.5%)
Sexualization Objectification	/ 1 (2%)	0 (0%)	7 (14%)	5 (10%)	13 (6.5%)
Gendered Insults	3 (6%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (6%)	6 (3%)
Emotional Support Parasocial	/ 3 (6%)	5 (10%)	5 (10%)	9 (18%)	22 (11%)
Humor / Sarcasm	3 (6%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	2 (4%)	6 (3%)
Harassment / Cyberbullying	2 (4%)	2 (4%)	4 (8%)	2 (4%)	10 (5%)
Ethnic / Nationality Hate	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	1 (2%)	2 (1%)
Success-Related Hate	0 (0%)	2 (4%)	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	5 (2.5%)
Comparisons	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	2 (1%)
Total Comments	50 (100%)	50 (100)	50 (100%)	50 (100%)	200 (100%)

Figure 2: Female celebrities category-wise comment distribution

Male Celebrities

The data presented in table 3 indicated that male celebrities receives a substantial number (103) of comments in admiration and praise category, that makes 51.5% of the total 400 comments received by all four celebrities combined. Second most populated area is neutral interaction with 28 (14%) comments. Atif Aslam receives 3 (6%) of the comments related to body shaming/ appearance attack out of total 4 comments combined, international celebrities Shawn and Timothee received no such comments. Additionally, out of total 3 comments related to moral/ religious policing were belong to Atif Aslam's posts. Timothee received the maximum 8 (16%) comments out of 9 falls under the category of sexualization/objectification. The data revealed that Atif Aslam is the only male celebrity who received maximum comments falls under the categories of gendered insults and comparison with 2 (4%) and 7 (14%) subsequently. Similarly Timothee and Shawn received maximum comments falling under the categories of Humor and Sarcasm, Harrasment/cyberbullying. Micro analysis of data indicated that Timothee has receive maximum 7 (14%) comments related to humor/sarcasm and 2 (4%) of harassment/cyberbullying; Shaen received 2 (4%) and 2 (4%) in each category. Additionally, They both received (Timothee, 4; Shawn, 2) comments coded under the category of success related hate; however both Pakistani celebrities did not receive any under this category. Another category that has maximum comment 21 (10.5%) is emotional support/parasocial interactions, where Shawn has receive maximum comments 9 (18%) along with Fawad Khan with 8 (16%) and Timothee received 4 (8%). It was also noted that none has received comments related to ethnic/ nationality hate which is interesting when compared with the

female celebrities. Over all data (see Table 3; Chart 3) of male celebrities elaborated that male celebrities received more comments related to Admiration & Praise, Neutral Interaction and Emotional Support/Parasocial Interactions and the minimum interactions were observed in Moral/ Religious policing and Gendered Insult, all comments under these categories were noted under Pakistani celebrities posts.

Table 3: *Male celebrities category-wise comment distribution*

Category	Atif Aslam	Fawad Khan	Timothée Chalamet	Shawn Mendes	Total (Male)
Admiration & Praise	27(54%)	27 (54%)	22 (44%)	27 (54%)	103 (51.5%)
Neutral Interaction	8 (16%)	10 (20%)	7 (14%)	3 (6%)	28 (14%)
Body Shaming / Appearance Attacks	3 (6%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (2%)
Moral/Religious Policing	3 (6%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (1.5%)
Sexualization Objectification	/ 0 (0%)	1 (2%)	8 (16%)	0 (0%)	9 (4.5%)
Gendered Insults	2 (4%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	3 (1.5%)
Emotional Support Parasocial	/ 0 (0%)	8 (16%)	4 (8%)	9 (18%)	21 (10.5%)
Humor / Sarcasm	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	2 (4%)	7 (14%)	10 (5%)
Harassment / Cyberbullying	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	2 (4%)	2 (4%)	5 (2.5%)
Ethnic / Nationality Hate	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)
Success-Related Hate	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	4 (8%)	2 (4%)	6 (3%)
Comparisons	7 (14%)	0 (0%)	1 (2%)	0 (0%)	8 (4%)
Total Comments	50	50	50	50	200

Figure 3: Male celebrities Category-wise comments distribution

Female Vs Male Comparison

The data presented a significant insight into gendered patterns of comments where the male celebrities have receive significantly higher number (103) of comments fall under the category of Admiration & Praise as compare to female which is 67 out of total 170 comments combined. Similarly the ratio of comments fall under the categories of Body Shaming/Appearance Attacks; Moral/ Religious Policing; Sexualization/Objectification; Gendered Insult; Humor/Sarcasm; Harrasment/Cyberbullying; Ethnic/Nationality Hate; Success Related Hate; Comparison depicted a significant Gendered patterns where women were observed to be treated differently and received more critical and hate comments than men, Women celebrities receive 24 comments out of total 28 falls under the category of Body Shaming/ Appearance attack; 11 out of 14 related to moral/religious policing; 13 out of 22 under category of Sexualization/Objectification; Gendered insult include 6 out of 9, 10 out 15 comments were of harassment/cyber bullying. Similar patterns have been observed in category of ethnic/nationality hate, however the categories of success related hate and comparison the male celebrities received more comments than women (Table 4; Graph 4)

Table 4: Comparative analysis of comment categories of female celebrities with male celebrities

Category	Total (Female)	Total (Male)	Total Comments
Admiration & Praise	67 (33.5%)	103 (51.5%)	170 (43%)
Neutral Interaction	32 (16%)	28 (14%)	60 (15%)
Body Shaming / Appearance Attacks	24 (12%)	4 (2%)	28 (7%)

Moral/Religious Policing	11 (5.5%)	3 (1.5%)	14 (3.5%)
Sexualization / Objectification	13 (6.5%)	9 (4.5%)	22 (5.5%)
Gendered Insults	6 (3%)	3 (1.5%)	9 (2.25%)
Emotional Support / Parasocial	22 (11%)	21 (10.5%)	43 (10.75%)
Humor / Sarcasm	6 (3%)	10 (5%)	16 (4%)
Harassment / Cyberbullying	10 (5%)	5 (2.5%)	15 (3.75%)
Ethnic / Nationality Hate	2 (1%)	0 (0%)	2 (0.5%)
Success-Related Hate	5 (2.5%)	6 (3%)	11 (2.75%)
Comparisons	2 (1%)	8 (4%)	10 (2.5%)
Total Comments	200	200	400

Figure 4: Comparative analysis of comments

Discussion and Conclusion

RQ-1: Comments categories more frequently appeared in male comments vs female celebrities' comments sections

The data represented a significant gendered pattern of comments appeared under the selected post of male and female celebrities. The most frequently appeared category in male and female celebrities section include Admiration and praise, however it was noted that male celebrities received more comments (103) than female (67) out of 176 (Table 4; chart 4). Category Neutral Interaction is the second most populated category where female celebrities received 32 and male celebrities received 28 out of 60 comments. The category of Social / Parasocial interactions is third most appeared category with 43 comments, maximum comments were under the female celebrities posts. However, the combined frequency of negative comments also reflected a significant number of comments that is 127 out of which women received 79 and male celebrities received 48. The frequently appeared category of all negative comment categories is Body shaming/ Appearance attack (Table 4)

RQ 2: Influence of nationality on the type of comments received by male and female celebrities
It has been observed by the researchers that gendered patterns are same for both the International and Pakistani female celebrities for negative comments fall under various categories. However, the Pakistani male celebrities (especially Atif Aslam) received more hate comments than the International celebrities. The comments under their posts reflected more positive engagements. Hence the data conforms the already prevalent assumption on gendered trends and reflected societal treatment of women in general as well (Table 2; Table 3; Table 4)

RQ 3: Difference between the ways male and female celebrities are treated in their comment section

The data presented in Table 4 showed that the categories include Admiration and Praise; Neutral interaction; Emotional support/Parasocial interaction showed same treatment for both genders. However, the categories of Body shaming /Appearance Attack, Moral /Religious Policing, Sexualization / Objectification; Gendered Insults; Harassment/ Cyberbullying; Ethnic / Nationality Hate mirrored significantly different treatment of both Pakistani and International women celebrities. Two categories Humor/ Sarcasm and Comparison have more comments under male celebrities' posts than women. The researchers noted more critical and

hateful comments under female celebrities' posts and comparatively mild treatment for male counterparts.

In general the findings of this study are very clear and consistent in showing strong gendered patterns in how people respond to celebrities online. It was observed that digital spaces such as Instagram are continuing to shape the treatment of celebrities both international and local on the basis of gender. The data highlighted the gendered pattern of how these celebrities were admired, criticized or victimized. Though, positive engagements were also highlighted but the difference in the nature of negative engagements for men and women reflective of prevailing gendered norms in society. For Pakistani female celebrities like Hania Amir and Mahira Khan, admiration was still the largest category, but the combined presence of body shaming, appearance critiques, and moral policing made up a third of all comments signals that women remain more vulnerable to culturally conditioned forms of online scrutiny. Even when women are praised, their visibility is often filtered through expectations of modesty, morality, and attractiveness. This mirrors findings from previous work showing that women in South Asian public spaces face intensified regulation of their appearance and conduct. The moral policing directed at Mahira (10%) and Hania (8%) also directly aligns with broader research showing that Pakistani audiences often use religious and cultural norms to frame criticism of female celebrities.

International female celebrities such as Zendaya and Selena experienced another version of the same gendered pattern. While both received more positive than negative engagement overall, Zendaya's comment section included the highest level of ethnic based criticism in the entire dataset, revealing how racism and gendered hate often intersect in public responses (this idea is also previously discussed in global online harassment literature). Both Zendaya and Selena also experienced more sexualization and objectification compared to Pakistani women, which fits global findings that female celebrities in Western media face sexualized commentary as a key form of online hostility.

International male celebrities, however, showed the starkest contrast. Timothée Chalamet and Shawn Mendes both received extraordinarily high levels of admiration, often framed through parasocial attachment expressions of emotional closeness, nostalgia, and affection. The near absence of moral policing or appearance based critique illustrates that male celebrities can occupy digital space without having their morality, clothing, or body scrutinized.

in the same way. Even when Timothée received objectifying comments (16%), they were expressed as playful desire rather than degrading judgment. This again aligns with parasocial interaction theory, which suggests audiences feel more comfortable idealizing male figures as approachable or emotionally accessible. This also aligned with the theory of Para-social interaction, which posits that the audience perceived male figures as more approachable and accessible. Collectively the findings of the data collected from the comments under the activities generated by all eight celebrities, reinforced these gendered contrasts. The data collectively indicated that female celebrities received around 33.5% admirations as compare to their male counterpart (51.5%), indicated that men are more likely to receive more positive reinforcement from their followers. Moreover, it was also noted that female celebrities received higher number of negative comments including moral policing, which was more visible for Pakistani women than for international women. Hence, indicated that the cultural context not only shapes the amount of hate but also the frame it accordingly. These patterns reflected that gendered hate is designed by both the global patterns of digital misogyny and local cultural norms. Moreover, it also established that humor and sarcasm operate differently for men and women, such as humor toward men (e.g., Timothée, Shawn) framed as playful or affectionate, whereas humor or sarcasm directed at women framed as mocking or belittling undertone. Lastly, para-social attachment appeared more in male celebrities comment sections which indicated that the followers are more comfortable in expressing emotional closeness to men than women. This imbalance indicated that how gendered expectations are shaping the boundaries of digital closeness. Overall, the findings underscore how Instagram comment sections resonated with the long standing societal norms even in different cultural existences. Positive comments dominated, but the context of negative comments revealed prevailing deep gender biases.

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